

Pomegranate Extract: Exploring Its Chemical Characteristics, Pharmacological Properties, And Health-Benefits

Somnath Lature*, Mayur V. Partole¹, Harsh D. Khare², Akshada B. Pimparkar³,
Prerna O. Singh⁴.

Department of Pharmaceutics Shri Pandit Baburao Chaughule College of Pharmacy Bhiwandi, Maharashtra
421308. India

Corresponding author

Name: Mayur V. Partole

1. Abstract

The fruit of the *Punica granatum* plant yields pomegranate extract, which has become well-known for its diverse phytochemical makeup and possible health advantages. This extract's potent antioxidant action is attributed to its high concentration of polyphenolic components, including anthocyanins and punicalagin's. These antioxidants are essential in the fight against oxidative stress, which is a major contributor to the emergence of chronic illnesses. Pomegranate extract has shown various medicinal qualities in pharmacology, such as cardioprotective, anti-inflammatory, and anti-cancer activities. According to research, it can promote programmed cell death (apoptosis) and limit the growth of cancer cells of different types, including breast and prostate malignancies. Additionally, research indicates that pomegranate extract may enhance lipid profiles and reduce blood pressure, improving cardiovascular health. Pomegranate extract has also been linked to positive impacts on metabolic health, such as enhanced insulin sensitivity and better weight control. By inhibiting the growth of germs associated with gum disease and tooth plaque, its antibacterial qualities help improve oral health. In conclusion, pomegranate extract is a wonderful natural substance with a wide range of intricate pharmacological and chemical traits. Its importance in preventive health initiatives is highlighted by its incorporation into dietary practices and possible medicinal applications. To clarify its methods of action and maximise its application in therapeutic used, more research is necessary.

Keywords: Pomegranate, panica. granatum, Phytochemicals, Antioxidant, Health-promoting.

2. Introduction

Pomegranates are edible fruits belonging to the Punicaceae family, growing interest in cultural, traditional, and medicinal applications across the globe; renowned as the "fruit of Eden" for its delectable flavor and health-promoting properties [1]. They are cultivated in Iranian-native pomegranates and grow abundantly throughout the Arabian Peninsula, Afghanistan, and India, especially in Maharashtra, which accounts for more than 70% of the country's crop production.[2]. India grows pomegranates in a range of climates, but its deep loam soils and warm, dry weather are ideal for growing the Bhagwa variety. In most cases, propagation requires hardwood cuttings.

The seeds are generating a lot of interest in the study because they include lipids, phytosterols, and polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs), among other bioactive substances. The majority of plant oils have PUFAs in a cis configuration, but some also have trans double bonds, which have an impact on the oils' nutritional value. Studies show that 65% to 80% of the punicic acid in bitter gourds and pomegranates, which are grown all over the world but especially in Mediterranean regions, is present in their seed oils. Pomegranate phytochemical concentration varies depending on variety, extraction techniques, climate, location, and production methods. Studies reveal notable variations in the amounts of phenolic compounds in different kinds; for instance, the Bhagwa variety has higher concentrations of phytochemicals than the Ganesh type. In addition, pomegranates from desert climates usually have lower organic acid content and higher concentrations of phenolic compounds than pomegranates from Mediterranean climates.[3] [4]

Primary metabolites including sugars, lipids, and fatty acids, as well as secondary metabolites like tannins, organic acids, phenolic acids (including gallic acid, ellagic acid (EA), and caffeic acid), anthocyanins, flavonoids, vitamins, and terpenes, are among the bioactive components of pomegranates.[5] Pomegranates are known for their powerful antioxidant qualities, which are mainly attributed to their polyphenol content. These compounds also help prevent oxidative damage, which is connected to several health problems, such as aging and cardiovascular disorders. These include organic acids, sterols, triterpenoids, fatty acids, alkaloids, and other advantageous phytochemicals like flavonoids, condensed tannins, and hydrolyzable tannins [6].

3. Phytochemical Composition of Different Parts of the Plants

1. Fruits: Pomegranate arils have a tangy and sweet flavor and are made up of 78% pulp and 22% seeds. They consist of 85% water, 5% bioactive substances, and 10% carbohydrates (mostly fructose and glucose) [4]. Arils get their red color from a combination of polyphenols, including flavonoids and anthocyanins, hydrolyzed tannins, ellagitannins (like punicalagin), and amino acids like alanine and glutamine [7]. The range of juice anthocyanin content is 9–115 mg/L

2. Seeds: Pomegranate seed oil (PSO) is extracted from pomegranate seeds and makes up 11% of the fruit's weight. PSO contains a lot of fats, most of which are polyunsaturated (91.53%), followed by monounsaturated (7.55%) and saturated (6.82%) fats [9]. Punicic acid has notable health advantages.[8] Research has demonstrated that conjugated α -linoleic acid helps prevent skin cancer and treat diabetes. Possess antioxidant qualities, lowers inflammation, and stops obesity. Punicic acid, which has strong anti-inflammatory and cancer-prevention properties, is the most common. The oil also contains amino acids like glutamate and phenylalanine in addition to fibers and coumarins [10].

3. Leaves: Pomegranate leaves are slender and lustrous, and they are used for tea, spices, infusions, and extracts in folk medicine. Aqueous/alcohol extract from pomegranate leaves is high in luteolin of note, 23 substances (11 phenolic acids, 8 tannins, 3 anthocyanins, and 1 flavonoid) were identified by chromatographic technique, and the largest compound resulted in EA (43.14 ± 0.57 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$ of the fraction) [11]. Depending on the age of the plant, leaves can also contain varying percentages of minerals and alkaloids [12].

4. Flowers: The round pink petals of *P. granatum* blooms are roughly 3 cm broad [13]. The blooms are inedible, but their extracts have been used to treat bacterial infections, inflammation, diabetes, and bronchitis. They are rich in phenolic acids such as gallic acid and have notable concentrations of phytochemicals like quercetin and catechin [14].

5. **Peel:** Pomegranate peel (PP) waste is referred to as "superfruit" waste since it makes up around 50% of the fruit and is valued as a by-product for extracting bioactive chemicals. [15]. In comparison to the edible component, it has higher levels of phytonutrients and substantial amounts of lipids such as oleic, palmitic, and linoleic acids. 51 substances, including phenolic and citric acids, were found in PP extract according to a study [16].

4. Pomegranate Extraction Technique:

1. Extraction of Pomegranate Simple Stirring Technique

For the analysis of plant materials and the recovery of bioactive components, extraction is essential. One popular technique that is influenced by the ingredients, types of solvents, and extraction procedures is simple stirring.[16]. Studies reveal that pomegranate peels, which are high in antioxidants, are frequently disregarded when making juice. Juice made solely of arils yields fewer antioxidants than whole pomegranates [17]. Common solvents include water, ethanol, and methanol; however, they may also co-extract undesirable materials. Selectivity is provided by ethyl acetate, and in just two minutes of extraction, water proves to be a highly efficient green solvent with a high antioxidant content

2. Extraction Of Pomegranate Seed Oil Using Soxhlet Extractor (Solvent Extractor)

Soxhlet extraction is performed on 50g of powdered pomegranate seed using petroleum ether (60–80°C) as the solvent. The solvent vaporizes, fills the thimble with warm solvent, and then condenses back. This cyclical process makes it possible to extract non-volatile components efficiently and concentrates the desired substance in the distillation flask [18]

3. Extraction Of Pomegranate Peel by Using Microwave-Assisted Extraction (MAE)

Microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) uses microwave energy to heat a solvent and plant matrix to effectively extract bioactive compounds from pomegranate peel. To increase surface area, the peels are dried and ground. They are then combined in a microwave reactor with the right solvent chosen by the desired chemicals. The mixture is cooled and filtered after radiation to remove any solid remnants from the liquid extract. A bioactive component analysis is performed on the resultant extract using methods such as HPLC or spectrophotometry [15].[19].

5. Chemical characteristics of Pomegranate extract:

P. granatum is a phytochemical mixture. The bark of the Fez plant contains phenolics, such as polyphenols, flavonoids, sterols, and polyterpenes, which can be extracted using methanol. With values of $272.82 \pm 32.05 \mu\text{g/mL}$ and $387.25 \pm 1.75 \mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively, flavonoids and phenolics are the most common components. However, there are no alkaloids or saponins in the bark [20]. Additionally, it was discovered A novel alkaloid called Punicagranine-1 is present in the peel[21]. The plant's flavonoids promote both cognitive improvement and cardioprotective effects. These flavonoids can support cardioprotective actions against cancer and improve memory through cognitive rehabilitation. In contrast, the fruit's skin still has the highest concentration of chemical components. Comparing extracts from aqueous peels to controls, learning and memory are considerably improved. Higher quantities of active chemicals are produced by ethanol extracts [12]. The herb possesses anthelmintic and antiparasitic properties. It is rich in vitamins, minerals, and amino acids. The compounds punicalin, punicalagin, and ellagic acid are significant, along with several other bioactive substances [22]. Pomegranates also include other beneficial compounds such as lignans, vitamin C, fatty acids, organic acids, xanthonoids, proanthocyanins, sterols, terpenes, tannins, flavonoids, phenolics, and alkaloids. The following chemical structures draw attention to these phytochemical groups:

1. **Alkaloids:** Pellitorine is one of the alkaloids that were isolated from *P. granatum*. According to [38], there is ongoing debate on pellitorine's presence. Peltierine, however, was found to have anti-cancerous qualities. Pseudocelletierine, N-methylpelletierine, isopelletierine, 1-pelletierine, and di-pelletierine are among the pelletierine

derivative chemicals that can be discovered in pomegranates [23]. Caffeine and pyridium chloride are other pomegranate alkaloids that have been discovered in (Fig.1).[22]

Fig. 1. Chemical structures of alkaloid compound isolated from pomegranate

2. **Anthocyanins:** The bioactive substances known as anthocyanins are what give pomegranates their color during the ripening process [24]. Elphinidin, cyanidin, and pelargonidin are the most well-known anthocyanin molecules. Additionally, it was discovered. Vitamin A is one of the bioactive substances (Fig. 2). Cyanidin-3-O-pentoxide, pelargonidin-3-O-glucoside, cyanidin-3-O-glucoside, and delphinidin-3-O-glucoside are further identified anthocyanin component compounds have been discovered in (Fig.2) [25].

Fig.2. Chemical structures of anthocyanins/anthocyanidins compounds isolated from pomegranate.

3. **Tannins:** The fruit pomegranate is rich in polyphenols and has tannins in both the seeds and the peel. Anti-microbial and anti-viral [26]. qualities are just two of the pharmacological attributes of pomegranates that are directly related to the bioactive molecules called tannins. Gallotannins and ellagitannins are two other tannin derivatives that can be discovered in pomegranates. 1,2, 3-Tri-O-galloyl- β -4C1-glucose, 2-O-Galloylpunicalin, 3,3'-Di-O-methyl ellagic acid, 3,3'4'-Tri-O-methyl ellagic acid, castalagin, castalin, casuarinin, corilagin, epicatechin, flavogallonic acid, gallagic acid, gallagigylidilacton, granatin A/B, lagerstannin C, pedunculagin, punicacortein A, B, C, and D, punicafolin, punicalagin, punicalin α , and β punicalagin are among the various isolated tannins from pomegranates component compounds have been discovered in (Fig.3)[27].

Fig. 3. Chemical structures of tannins compound isolated from pomegranate.

4. Flavonoids: Due to the abundance of flavonoid bioactive compounds, pomegranates have antibacterial, antioxidant, anti-atherosclerosis, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, and anti-cancerous pharmacological effects [28]. The entire fruit, including the peels, seeds, leaves, juice, flowers, pericarps, and barks. Has been found to contain flavonoids. Commonly recognized *P. granatum* flavonoids are shown in Several common flavonoids were also found [27] including. luteolin, taxifolin, apigenin, chrysin, cyanidin, lutein, and glucoside. Flavonoids from pomegranate Component compounds have been discovered in (Fig.4)

Fig. 4. Chemical structures of flavonoids isolated from pomegranate.

5. Phenolics: discovered phenolic chemicals [29], including punicalin, gallic acid, ellagic acid, and pyrogallol. Moreover, the study found phenolics such as caffeic acid, coumaric acid, salicylic acid, vanillic acid, and sesamin. Additionally, it has been discovered that phenolic compounds in *P. granatum* suppress the activities of α -glucosidase. Phenolics from pomegranate component compounds have been found in (Fig.5).[25]

Fig. 5. Chemical structures of phenolic compounds isolated from pomegranate.

6. Proanthocyanidins: The presence of proanthocyanidins, tannins, and flavonoids—bioactive compounds, as well as their pharmacological activities, have increased interest in medicinal plants [30] Proanthocyanidins aid in releasing catechins, which are vital substances needed to work in concert with ascorbic acid to inhibit free radicals [32]. Furthermore, procyanidin dimers B2 and B3, arabinose, xylose, galactose, mannose, and rhamnose are proanthocyanidin-containing substances in pomegranates component compounds have been discovered (Fig.6).[30]

Fig. 6. Chemical structures of proanthocyanidins isolated from pomegranate.

7. Sterols: Sterols are the least abundant bioactive substances in pomegranates [41] And are naturally occurring steroids [30]. The primary role of sterols is to lower plasma levels of low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C)

and the absorption of cholesterol. [50]. Asiatic acid is the main sterol compound mentioned.[31] Identified cholesterol, sitosterol, and stigmasterol in Figure 7. *P. granatum* seeds contain the sex steroids estrone, testosterone, and estriol. Pomegranates are known to contain similar sterol compounds, such as daucosterol, sitosterol-acetate, and campesterol.[31].

Fig. 7. Chemical structures of sterol compounds isolated from pomegranate.

8. Terpenes and terpenoids: The primary bioactive components of concentrated and essential oils are terpenes and terpenoids [33]. Terpenes and terpenoids have several pharmacological advantages, including anti-inflammatory, anti-tumor, antioxidant, and antiallergic properties [56]. Terpenoids, which are classed as secondary metabolites and are produced by medicinal plants, are crucial for disease resistance[32]. Terpenes are made up of a variety of components, such as monoterpenes, which are volatile substances. And are present in trace amounts in pomegranates. 3-carene are the volatile chemicals associated with terpenes, as shown in Fig. 8.[27] Moreover, aldehydes, alcohol, and oxygenated monoterpenes are recognized.

Fig. 8. Terpenoids compound isolated from pomegranate.

9. Xanthonoids: Natural polyphenolic substances called xanthonoids have several pharmacological properties, such as anti-oxidant, anti-bacterial, anti-fungal, and anti-viral properties [34]. The xanthonoid compound of *P. granatum* identified from the peel is mangiferin, component compounds have been discovered in (Fig. 9) [35].

Fig. 9. Chemical structures of xanthonoids isolated from pomegranate.

10. Lignans: Plants are shielded against pathogens by lignans, which are secondary metabolites [36]. There have been claims that they contain anti-inflammatory, and cardiovascular disease prevention properties. Four main lignans were identified from the plant juice [33].cycloariciserol, syringaresinol, pinoresinol. However. Report that *P. granatum* seeds and whole fruit contain many lignans, such as medioresinol and matairesinol (Fig. 10). Furthermore, lignans found in *P. granatum* include considering, isohydroxymatairesinol, isolariciresinol, phyligenin, secoisolariciresinol, pomegralignan, and punicatannin.

Fig. 10. Chemical structures of lignans compound isolated from pomegranate

11. Saccharides: Pomegranate saccharides have been found to have anti-diabetic pharmacological activity [37], as well as immunomodulatory actions that improve and symptoms of hypersensitivity that are alleviated [38]. The primary sugars present in pomegranates are sucrose, fructose, glucose, and maltose. Saccharides from pomegranate Component compounds have been discovered in (Fig.11).

Fig. 11. Chemical structures of saccharides compound isolated from pomegranate.

12. Vitamin C: According to [27], vitamin C is found in pomegranate juice, Vitamin C is essential in providing nutritional and therapeutic effects [39]. Moreover, the consumption of Pomegranate. Component compounds have been discovered in (Fig. 12).

Fig. 12. Chemical structures of vitamin compounds isolated from pomegranate

6. Pharmacological Properties of Pomegranate

1. Antioxidant properties: Oxidative stress (OS) produces toxic compounds that can advance cancer. Pomegranate's flavonoids and polyphenols reduce inflammatory and cardiovascular diseases by inhibiting OS. Green tea has three times the antioxidant activity of flavonoids and anthocyanidins found in pomegranate juice and seed oil. These extracts scavenge hydroxyl radicals and superoxide anions. According to studies, pomegranate peel methanolic extracts have strong antioxidant properties when evaluated using a variety of assays. Additionally,

pomegranate juice lowers the activation of procarcinogens and provides protection against oxidative stress and cell damage. It also lowers cholesterol and LDL. In contrast to pomegranates, NSAIDs can impair heart health. In osteoarthritis, pomegranate may also prevent collagen deterioration.[40]

2. Anti-Cardiovascular Effects: High levels of low HDL-C and high LDL-C are indicators of dyslipidemia, which is a major risk factor for coronary heart disease. A study looked at how 40 grams of concentrated pomegranate juice affected the lipid profiles of people with type II diabetes who had hyperlipidaemia [41].

3. Anti-inflammatory activities: *Punica granatum* is one of the numerous medicinal plants that have anti-inflammatory properties. Inflammation is essential for the body's defense. Because *P. granatum* has skin care qualities and encourages hair development (as demonstrated by research on mice), it is commonly used in cosmetics. Punicagranine 1 is a chemical that has strong inhibitory effects. Pomegranate extracts have been shown in studies to decrease pro-inflammatory indicators such as PGE2 and NO, inhibit COX-2 and iNOS, and modify pathways by activating PPAR γ and AP-1, which strengthens macrophage defense systems.[42]

4. Anti-cancer: Complementary and alternative medicines, including pomegranate extract (PE) and punicalagin, show promise in cancer control. PE reduced COX-2 expression and prevented breast cancer in rats. In Sarcoma-180 mice, PE and 2-methoxy estradiol (2-ME) improved lifespan and reduced tumor volume. Ellagic acid induced apoptosis and cell cycle arrest in prostate cancer and leukemia models, while delphinidin caused apoptosis in resistant colon cancer cells. These findings highlight the potential of natural compounds in cancer therapy [43].

5. Anti-diabetic properties: Immune system problems and organ dysfunction can result from cardiovascular risk factors such as diabetes and insulin resistance. Insulin deficiency causes chronic hyperglycemia, while food and obesity are major causes of type II diabetes. While floral extracts can lower blood glucose and block alpha-glucosidase, pomegranate peel extract may protect against oxidative stress and hyperglycemia. Pomegranate helps diabetic nephropathy patients' lipid profiles as well. Pomegranate extracts have been shown in studies to lower triglycerides and increase antioxidants in diabetic rats. In addition, pomegranate flower extract increases insulin sensitivity and glucose metabolism via increasing GLUT-4 expression, primarily because gallic acid, and polyphenols block digestive enzymes.[42][43].

6. Antiviral and anti-COVID-19 potential: Alkaloids, polyphenols, and coumarins found in *P. granatum* suppress the multiplication of viruses[73] Polyphenols with potent antiviral effects include punicalagin and ellagic acid. Pomegranate peel extract (PPE) has been shown in recent experiments to strongly inhibit SARS-CoV-2 by preventing its spike glycoprotein interaction with ACE2, with inhibition levels as high as 74%. Furthermore, PPE suppressed important genes related to viral entrance and replication. These results point to the efficacy and safety of PPE and its compounds in preventing SARS-CoV-2 infection, which calls for more in vivo testing.[44]

7. Anti-malaria properties: The *Plasmodium* parasite is the cause of malaria, a disease that is common throughout Africa and can have serious health consequences. According to research, pomegranate peel extract effectively combats *Plasmodium falciparum* and *Plasmodium vivax* through its anti-malarial capabilities. The effectiveness of methanol extracts against *Plasmodium berghei*, *Plasmodium chabaudi*, and *Plasmodium chabaudi* also highlights the potential of pomegranates as natural remedies.[45]

8. Cell cycle arrest: The cell cycle, which includes G1, S, G2, and M phases, regulates cell division. Pomegranate extracts can alter this cycle, particularly by halting progression in the G0/G1 phase, suppressing growth in mouse mammary cancer cells. Metabolites like urolithins and elegantin's reduce HT-29 cell proliferation and clonogenic efficiency by inducing apoptosis and causing cell cycle arrest in the G0/G1 and G2/M phases.[46]

Research Through Innovation

9. Other potential Effects: By enhancing sperm quality, pomegranate's androgenic qualities can effectively treat male infertility[80]. Pectin, which can be used as a food coloring and additive, is found in its peels. Pomegranate phenolic chemicals boost cognition, strengthen muscles, and have anti-aging and anti-Alzheimer properties. Furthermore, fruit pericarp extracts show biocompatibility and the capacity to prevent the formation of biofilms.[47][48].

Fig.13 Summary of the chemical composition, pomegranate extraction technique, chemical characteristics, and pharmacological activities of pomegranate.

7. Conclusion:

The health advantages of pomegranates, with their juice, peel, and seeds full of beneficial bioactive chemicals, have led to a rise in their intake. This ancient fruit, which comes from the Mediterranean, is well known for its medicinal qualities and can be used to treat coughs, dandruff, and digestive disorders. Improved control of infections, cancer, inflammation, obesity, diabetes, and malaria has been associated with *P. granatum*. Through blocking the interaction between ACE2 and the SARS-CoV-2 spike glycoprotein, it has been shown to have anti-COVID-19 potential in recent studies. Pomegranates, which are high in antioxidants and minerals, work to fend off dangerous free radicals and can improve several of health issues by influencing pathways like PPARs, NF- κ B, and Nrf. A diet rich in fruits and vegetables may lower the risk of chronic disease when pomegranates are included in it.

8. References:

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